

**AN APPROACH TO OPTIMIZE INTERFACES IN CARBON/ALUMINIUM
AND CARBON/MAGNESIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES ELABORATED
BY HOT PRESSING.**

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ABSTRACT : O.N.E.R.A has developed a liquid infiltration technique under moderate pressure (10-20 MPa) for processing carbon reinforced aluminium and magnesium matrix composites. Unidirectional composites with longitudinal tensile strength as high as 1400 MPa have been obtained both on aluminium and magnesium composites (volume fraction 50%). Longitudinal Young modulus of 320 GPa has also been measured on a FT700 /AZ61 indicating a fairly good infiltration of the composite. As the properties of these composites are highly dependent on the interphase structure and composition, the present study describes the approach adopted to develop materials having high tensile strength via the optimization of processing parameters, matrix composition and fibre coatings.

Keywords : Metal Matrix Composites-Aluminium- Hot Pressing- Coatings- Interfaces.

1. INTRODUCTION

Potentially, aluminium and magnesium matrix composites reinforced with long carbon fibres have mechanical properties (specific strength and stiffness) and physical characteristics (electric and thermal conductivities, low thermal expansion coefficient) which are interesting for aerospace applications. However, the mechanical properties of the materials fabricated up to now have not yet reached the expected values and as a consequence, their industrial development has been slow. This situation results from difficulties met in controlling their fabrication and in optimizing the constituent properties, in particular the matrix/fibre interface.

The fibre/matrix interface plays several rôles : load transfer from matrix to fibres, mechanical fuse, wetting agent, diffusion barrier, etc. Designing optimized interfaces is a difficult exercise as it implies taking into account a large number of parameters, some of them being difficult to determine for lack of data and adequate modelling. Indeed the structure and the properties of C/Al and C/Mg are dependent on a variety of factors :

- the type of fibre and its surface microstructure (PAN- or pitch-based, high modulus or high strength),
- the nature of coating deposited onto the fibre (chemical composition, structure, mechanical properties, thickness, adhesion to the fibre),
- the matrix alloy composition (reaction kinetics with carbon of the fibre or with the coating, formation of brittle primary phases, of strengthening precipitates),
- the processing conditions (infiltration temperature, duration of interaction at high temperature, applied pressure).

Ideally, investigating such a problem requires different interrelated approaches :

- a semi-empirical work consisting in fabricating and characterizing composites in order to define

processing conditions and screen the most interesting systems for further in-depth studies,

- a physicochemical approach based on fine observations (T.E.M.) and microanalysis of the fibre/coating/matrix interfaces,

- a micromechanical approach, based both on numerical modelling of the load transfer and on experimental observations.

We have engaged a study along these lines for optimizing interfaces in carbon reinforced aluminium and magnesium matrix composites which have a high fibre volume fraction (typically 50%). Work has begun by the development of a fabrication process by liquid infiltration under moderate pressure [1, 2] and the development of a process for coating the fibres by LPCVD (low pressure chemical vapour deposition) [3].

In this paper, we present the mechanical results obtained with various systems and discuss them in the light of metallographic and microstructural investigations, and also with reference to available published data.

2. THE APPROACH

The tensile strength of unidirectional fibre reinforced composites having a Al or Mg matrix has been analyzed by different authors [4 -6]. The main conclusions to be drawn can be schematically summarized if we consider the two following extreme cases.

a/ An interfacial reaction occurs during fabrication and the fibre/matrix bonding is strong. In a tensile test, if the fibre-to-fibre distance is short, the rupture of one fibre will cause a stress concentration on the adjacent fibres. This overload can provoke the rupture of these fibres which will extend to the entire composite section. The fracture surface is planar. All the fibres are fractured in approximately the same plane and lie at the bottom of dimples formed by the deformation and necking of the ductile matrix.

In the case where the reaction is strong enough for the growth of a brittle phase, cracks initiated in this phase can propagate in the fibre and facilitate the occurrence of the process previously described.

This type of rupture, associated with ultimate strengths as low as 200 MPa, has been frequently recorded in C/Al composites due to the formation of Al_4C_3 at the interfaces.

Such a phenomena can also occur due to the presence of a brittle ceramic coating deposited on the fibre to act as a diffusion barrier. This effect has been described by Ochiai et al. [7] and Himbeault [8] who showed that the presence of an adherent brittle coating on the fibres can provoke a severe loss in mechanical strength for coating thicknesses exceeding 100 nm.

b/ The fibre is chemically inert regarding the matrix and the fibre/matrix bonding is "weak". In this case, cracks that appear in the weakest fibres may cause sufficient debonding at the interface so that the adjacent fibres are not affected. The stress concentration effect on the adjacent fibres is thus cancelled out. However the load transfer on the fibre fragments is not much efficient and the mechanical strength of the composite is not optimum. This behaviour is characterized by a longitudinal fracture surface with pull-out fragments extending over 100 μm or more. Typically this situation is encountered with Mg matrix composites reinforced with pitch-based uncoated fibres.

From these considerations it is clear that optimum mechanical strength implies that once a crack has initiated in a fibre, it must be deflected along the interface and its propagation must be controlled: on not too short a distance to avoid overloading the adjacent fibres, not too long to enable an efficient load transfer. If qualitatively the behaviour seems understood and can provide useful guidelines in the selection of constituents and process conditions, a significant effort for modelling these phenomena remains to be done, a complex task as it requires defining a local fracture criteria between dissimilar materials (fibre, coating, elasto-plastic metallic matrix) whose properties are not all known..

As far as the C/Mg composites are concerned, the work done with AZ61 matrix alloy (Mg-6%Al-1% Zn) and various fibres (M40, M40J, FT700) has lead without too much difficulty, given the lack of interfacial interaction, to high mechanical properties even if the ultimate strengths do not

reach optimum values.

The core of our effort has been devoted to the development of C/Al composites. Preliminary studies have been carried out on composites constituted of a commercially pure aluminium matrix (1199) reinforced with carbon fibres, either uncoated or coated with a SiC layer deposited by LPCVD or RCVD (reactive chemical vapour deposition) [9]. The composites were fabricated according to the same procedure as the C/magnesium materials, in particular with a cooling rate of 7.5°C/min. Invariably, these C/Al composites exhibited a type a/ fracture with low strength values due to an excessive interfacial interaction. In order to limit the extent and kinetics of the chemical reactions, the work has been reorientated along the following lines :

- The fabrication system was modified in order to increase the cooling rate up to 50°C/min, thus reducing the time during which the reinforcement is in contact with liquid aluminium.

- The commercially pure aluminium matrix was replaced by an Al-4.5wt%Mg alloy, decreasing the infiltration temperature by 25°C, thus slowing the reaction kinetics (comparative experiments conducted at 665°C with 1199 and Al-4.5 Mg alloy have shown that Mg addition decreases the reactivity of C/Al and SiC/Al systems [10]).

- Fibre coatings have been deposited by LPCVD : pyrolytic carbon coating (Cp) which has a weak shear strength, has been developed in order to provoke adequate debonding at the fibre-matrix interface. Duplex Cp + SiC coating has been evaluated in order to add the SiC diffusion barrier effect to mechanical fuse Cp.

The properties of the C/Al composites fabricated along these lines are presented in the following section.

3. TENSILE TESTS RESULTS AT 20°C ON UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

Tensile tests are carried out on composite specimen which dimension are 80*8*1 mm³.

TABLE 1. Composite elaborated with ex P.A.N High Resistance T800 fibre

Reference number	Matrix	Coating	Cooling rate (°C/min)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young Modulus (GPa)	Fibre Volume (%)	Ratio of UTS/ROM Value (%)
244	Al-4.5 Mg	no	50	285	151	45	11
215	Al-4.5 Mg	SiC-RCVD	50	451		51	16
231	Al-4.5 Mg	SiC-LPCVD	50	456	222	62	13
230	Al-4.5 Mg	Cp	50	1376	182	65	37.5
238	Al-4.5 Mg	Cp+SiC-LPCVD	50	741		59	22

Table 1 comment:

244 shows the important effect of the reactivity of the high resistance (HR) ex P.A.N T800 fibre with aluminium. At the fibre-matrix interface, a large number of Al₄C₃ needles have formed which size can be as important as 600 nm (Figure 1). In such a composite, the fracture surface is planar.

215 and 231 point out that, whatever the coating process, SiC is not a good diffusion barrier against aluminium at 640°C. Observations made by T.E.M associated with S.A.D show that the reaction layer at the interface consists of Al₄C₃. However, SiC seems to be a bit less reactive toward aluminium than carbon from T800.

230 : the improvement in mechanical strength associated with metallographic examinations of cross

sections and fracture surfaces of composites indicate that :

- Pyrolytic carbon is less reactive toward aluminium than carbon from T800 and SiC. This is confirmed by M.E.T examinations (not shown) indicating a much less important Al_4C_3 reaction layer. This is an important property to notice and may be explained by the lamellar microstructure of pyrolytic carbon which exhibits few active sites in contact with aluminium.

- " fibre pull-out " fragments with lengths of about 10 μm (Figure 2) are obtained, showing that pyrolytic carbon has played its role of mechanical fuse.

238 shows that no improvement is obtained with the double layer coating compared with Cp. This confirms that Cp is a best diffusion barrier than SiC. The improvement obtained with the double layer with regard to SiC is only due to the mechanical role of Cp.

Table 1 conclusion :

Very low mechanical properties are obtained with uncoated T800 fibre. An important improvement is obtained with Cp coating but the results are still far (37.5%) from the expected value calculated by the rule of mixture. This points out the absolute necessity for the High Resistance ex P.A.N fibre to have an efficient coating.

TABLE 2. Composites elaborated with ex P.A.N High Modulus M40 fibre.

Reference number	Matrix	Coating	Cooling rate (°C/min)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young Modulus (GPa)	Fibre Volume (%)	Ratio of UTS/ROM Value (%)
233	Al-4.5 Mg	SiC-LPCVD	50	340	215	61	20
232	Al-4.5 Mg	Cp	50	884	164	43	72
239	Al-4.5 Mg	Cp+SiC-LPCVD	50	302	201	61.5	17.5
246	Al-4.5 Mg	no	50	797	236	47	59
178	Mg-AZ61	no	7.5	853			

TABLE 3. Composites elaborated with Ex P.A.N High Modulus M40 J fibre.

Reference number	Matrix	Coating	Cooling rate (°C/min)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young Modulus (GPa)	Fibre Volume (%)	Ratio of UTS/ROM Value (%)
227	Al-1199	SiC-RCVD	50	482	199	58	18.6
223	Al-4.5 Mg	SiC-RCVD	50	845		52	36
243	Al-4.5 Mg	no	50	1144	211	46	55
174	Mg-AZ61	no	7.5	1410	200	47	66

Table 2 and 3 presents the mechanical properties of composites reinforced with M40 and M40 J which are both high modulus (HM) ex P.A.N fibres.

These fibres are less reactive toward aluminium (246, 243) than high resistance ex P.A.N fibre (244, table1). This may be attributed to the microstructure differences between the fibres, HM fibre surfaces containing less active sites than HR fibres[11].

The important and beneficial addition of magnesium is clearly seen when comparing 227 and 223. This effect may arise from two reasons : decrease of the processing temperature and the presence of the element Mg itself.

For both fibres, SiC coating seems to be more reactive with aluminium (233, 223) than carbon from the fibre. These results show how difficult it is to give a general conclusion about the chemical barrier effect of SiC. Pyrolytic carbon (232) only brings a slight improvement in the mechanical properties and the double layer (239) is as ineffective as SiC alone.

Although the Cp-coated M40 reinforced Al-4.5 Mg (232) displays a high mechanical strength relatively close to M40 reinforced AZ61 (246), the S.E.M examinations of composites rupture surface (Figure 3 and 4) reveal important differences related to the interface role. In the case of aluminium, very short pull-out lengths are obtained, indicating a rather strong fibre-matrix adhesion . On the other hand, "pull-out" lengths in the magnesium matrix are important (about 50 µm) , typical of a very weak adhesion between fibre and matrix.

Table 2 and 3 conclusion

In the case of high modulus ex P.A.N fibres, it does not appear absolutely necessary to coat the fibres with a chemical barrier as the fibre itself is not very reactive. It may be more effective to optimize the thickness of the pyrolytic carbon coating in order to optimize the decohesion length at the fibre (coating)-matrix interface.

TABLE 4 : Composites elaborated with Ex Pitch P55 fibre

Reference number	Matrix	Coating	Cooling rate (°C/min)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young Modulus (GPa)	Volume fraction (%)	Ratio of UTS/ROM Value (%)
147	Al-1199	SiC-LPCVD	7.5	421			
229	Al-4.5 Mg	SiC-LPCVD	50	601	162	45	60
228	Al-4.5 Mg	Cp	50	669	180	53	58
234	Al-4.5 Mg	Cp+SiC-LPCVD	50	404	173	58	32
245	Al-4.5 Mg	no	50	575	235	66	40
102	Al-1199	no	7.5	374			
137	Mg-AZ61	no	7.5	498			

Table 4 comment :

245 which represents about 40% of the rule of mixture confirms the weak reactivity of ex Pitch fibre.

The result 228 (about 58% of the rule of mixture) obtained with the ex Pitch P55 fibre corroborates the beneficial effect of the pyrolytic carbon coating.

The effect of SiC-LPCVD (147, 229) is about the same as Cp coating : this is attributed to the fact that this coating is not adherent to P55 fibre and more generally to ex Pitch fibre. So, the coating plays a role of mechanical fuse. S.E.M examinations of the rupture surface show that "pull-out" is obtained, and, at a higher magnification (figure 6), that the debonding takes place between fibre and SiC coating. SiC is however more reactive than Cp (229, 228) and the double layer Cp+SiC is once more ineffective.

Table 4 conclusion :

For P55 fibre, we can expect an improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite in

optimizing the pyrolytic carbon thickness in order to obtain further debonding, or in using a more effective chemical barrier coating in the duplex layer Cp+ barrier.

Table 5. Composites elaborated with HM ex Pitch FT700 fibre.

Reference number	Matrix	Cooling rate (°C/min)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Young Modulus (GPa)	Volume Fraction (%)	Ratio of UTS/ROM value (%)
235	Al-4.5 Mg	50	1010	270	49	61
200	Mg-AZ61	7.5	1122	320	57	58

Table 5 comment :

This table confirms the lower reactivity of ex Pitch fibre with aluminium compared with ex P.A.N fibres [12]. In that case, S.E.M examinations of rupture surfaces show that the interfacial behaviour is quite different than in ex P.A.N fibres. Very important "pull-out" lengths (above 100µm) are obtained in 235 (figure 5), about the same as in the magnesium based matrix composite, 200. This indicates that, surprisingly enough, the fibre-matrix adhesion is weak.

Table 5 conclusion :

Mechanical results should be improved by increasing interfacial adhesion. This result should be easily obtained by modifying the elaboration process, for example by increasing the elaboration temperature or decreasing the cooling rate.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The strategy adopted, which involves selection of a matrix alloy, a coating and adaptation of the processing conditions leads to remarkable results, as tensile strengths as high as 1400 MPa have been obtained. The results reported in this paper, on the mechanical properties of unidirectional carbon fibres / coating / matrix systems show how sensitive the longitudinal strength is, with respect to the interfacial characteristics.

The difference in reactivity of uncoated carbon fibres with aluminium is clearly seen on table 6.

TABLE 6. Reactivity of different fibres toward Al-4.5 Mg, cooling rate 50°C / min.

Fibre name	Supplier	Source	Fibre type	Fibre Tensile Strength (MPa)	Fibre Young Modulus (GPa)	Ultimate Composite Strength (MPa)	Fibre fraction (%)	Ratio of UTS/ROM Value (%)
T800	Toray	ex P.A.N	HR	5590	294	285	45	11
M40	Toray	ex P.A.N	HM	2740	400	797	47	59
M40J	Toray	ex P.A.N	HM	4400	377	1144	46	55
P55	Amoco	ex Pitch	HR	2100	380	575	66	40
FT700	Tonen	ex Pitch	HM	3300	700	1010	49	61

Fibres which are produced at carbonization stages (HR) are more reactive than fibres produced at graphitization stage (HM). This has already been observed on carbon / aluminium composite wires by Amateau [13], who links the high temperature heat treatment to the degree of preferred orientation of the fibre and establishes a relationship between the degree of graphitization and the Young Modulus. However, carbonized fibres, as T800, even though their surface is very reactive are still good candidates for reinforcing aluminium as they can potentially give, once coated, high strength composites.

It is to be noted that, in the case of very high modulus fibre, such as FT700, the interfacial adhesion is weak ; the strategy to improve mechanical properties consists in modifying the elaboration process (decreasing the cooling rate, increasing elaboration temperature, changing aluminium alloy). Fibre coating may not be necessary.

Among the coatings envisaged (SiC-LPCVD, SiC-RCVD, Cp), only those capable of playing a role of mechanical fuse are potentially interesting : Cp which has been incorporated in T800 and M40 /Al-4.5 Mg systems and SiC-LPCVD in P55 / Al-4.5 Mg. It should be pointed out however that further work is still to be done to optimize the coating characteristics (thickness, structure, ...).

The experimental data reported here provide a basis for establishing models which could give guidelines for optimizing the interfaces in metal matrix systems.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank D.R.E.T for partial financial support.

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Figure 1. Reaction zone in T800/ Al-4.5 Mg

Figure 2. T800/Cp/Al-4.5 Mg : Rupture Surface

Figure 3. M40/Cp/Al-4.5 Mg: Rupture Surface

Figure 4. M40/AZ61: Rupture Surface

Figure 5. FT700/Al-4.5 Mg : Rupture Surface

Figure 6. P55/1199 : Rupture Surface